

INVESTIGATION OF CORRUGATED LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE SHEAR LOADING

Daniel T. Filipovic¹ and Gerald R. Kress²

¹ CMASLab, Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich, Tannenstrasse 3, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland, fidaniel@ethz.ch, <http://www.structures.ethz.ch>

² CMASLab, Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich, Tannenstrasse 3, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland, gkress@ethz.ch, <http://www.structures.ethz.ch>

Keywords: Corrugation, Transverse Shear, Finite Element

ABSTRACT

One of the advantages of corrugated laminates is that they show a significant increase in bending stiffness as the corrugation amplitude is increased. However, the change in transverse shear stiffness is expected to remain modest. In order to investigate said effects, an efficient (planar) finite element formulation has been derived which can be used to calculate the response of a corrugated laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. The results provided by the presented model highlight peculiarities in the resulting shear stress distribution. A special emphasis is laid on the difference between plates and corrugated structures, which is demonstrated by comparing the transverse shear stresses in flat laminates to corrugated laminates for different lay-ups.

1 INTRODUCTION

Corrugated structures have been in use – both in mechanical and civil engineering – for decades. Regarding the geometry of the corrugations, a variety of possible shapes exists, whereas the circular, sinusoidal and the trapezoidal corrugations are among the most prominently used ones. Common to all corrugated structures is that they provide interesting stiffness properties that can be exploited in different kinds of applications.

Already Hugo Junkers used corrugated metal sheets in the airplane design of his Ju-52 [1, 2] due to their high bending stiffness and their high critical buckling load. The ability to achieve a high stiffness while maintaining a low weight is also the reason for the wide use of said structures in civil engineering, e.g. as roof, wall or floor elements.

The emergence and increasing use of carbon fiber reinforced polymers in the last decades has even extended the possibilities of working with corrugated structures. The anisotropy stemming from the geometry is complemented by the anisotropy of the material, i.e. the base laminate, thus enabling to achieve a high degree of anisotropy. Yokozeki et al. [3] proposed corrugated laminates as candidate materials for flexible skins in morphing wings. This is because they combine a high compliance along the corrugation direction with a high bending stiffness about the direction of corrugation. Thill et al. [8] as well as Xia et al. [9] have studied the aerodynamic effects of such a morphing wing solutions. A general overview of research on corrugated laminates in the context of morphing wings is given by Dayyani et al. [4] and Airolidi et al. [5].

Nature itself has used corrugated structures and their beneficial properties e.g. in the surface of shells or the wing profiles of insects [6]. The desire to imitate insect flight in micro-air vehicles has sparked interest in investigating the properties of the dragonfly wing. Levy and Seifert [7] have shown that at Reynolds numbers between 2000 and 8000 the corrugations in the dragonfly airfoil have an improving effect on the aerodynamic performance compared to an airfoil usually used in low Reynolds number regimes.

Evaluating the structural properties of corrugated laminates usually comes at a high computational cost due to the geometry with its large number of periods and the layer-wise modelling of the material imposed by the laminate. Researchers have therefore derived equivalent models, which allow to represent the structural response of a corrugated structure at low computational cost. An earlier derivation of equivalent properties was presented by Briassoulis [10], which derived improved

expressions for the flexural rigidities of corrugated shells. Xia et al. [11] presented a homogenization model for corrugation geometries of arbitrary shape. It was later extended by Wang et al. [12] in order to include effects of axial and bending coupling in case of fixed boundary conditions.

Kress and Winkler [13] have derived an analytical model for finding the substitute ABD-matrix of thin circular corrugated laminates. The finite element model presented by Kress and Winkler [15] is derived based on the same theoretical background. It does not have any restrictions regarding the thickness or the layup of the laminate, or the corrugation shape.

Manufacturing of corrugated laminates poses difficulties for large values of corrugation amplitudes, since the undercuts increase the complexity and cost of mold-based manufacturing methods. In order to mitigate this problem, Filipovic and Kress [14] have recently presented a mold-less manufacturing method for high-amplitude corrugated laminates, which is based on thermal deformation effects in thin-walled laminates.

2 MOTIVATION

One of the advantages of corrugated laminates is that they show a large increase in bending stiffness about the direction of corrugation. Depending on the exact lay-up and geometry, the stiffness can increase significantly, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Evolution of bending stiffness and transverse shear stiffness with increasing corrugation amplitude in a thin corrugated laminate.

Compared to that, the change in transverse shear stiffness with increasing corrugation amplitude is only marginal, which is expected to have a relevant influence on the structural behaviour of corrugated laminates [19]. In order to be able to investigate said effects, we have therefore derived a planar finite element routine, which can be used to efficiently characterize the response of a corrugated laminate under shear loading [16, 17].

The objective of this paper is to use said model in order to explain the dominating mechanisms in corrugated laminates subjected to transverse shear. As several theories exist for calculating shear stresses in plates, a special emphasis is laid on the peculiarities that come with the introduction of the corrugation.

3 RECALL OF MODEL AND LOAD CASE

The finite element model presented by Filipovic and Kress [16] was developed with the aim of reducing the computational cost of modelling a corrugated laminate with arbitrary lay-up subjected to shear. The model loading situation is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Illustration of the transverse shear load case.

On the one hand, the use of the unit cell approach in the model allows a considerable saving in computational effort: only one period of a larger structure is modeled. This inner solution can be enforced by imposing periodicity boundary conditions at either end of the unit cell.

On the other hand, the model requires a planar mesh only. It takes advantage of the fact that for the situation given in Fig. 2, the bending moment and the curvature distribution will vary linearly with x :

$$\kappa_{xx} \sim \kappa'_{xx} \cdot x \quad (1)$$

The curvature gradient κ'_{xx} shown in Eq. 1 serves as an input parameter for the finite element routine, as it is contained in the displacement field underlying the given FE routine. It takes advantage of the fact that the resulting inner shear force and shear stress distribution for the situation given in Fig. 2 will be independent of the out-of-plane coordinate, i.e.:

$$\tau_{xi} = f(y, z) \leftrightarrow F(x) = const. \quad (2)$$

Hence, also cross-sectional warping induced by the shear force is independent of x . Any contributions in the displacement field which depend on the out-of-plane coordinate x are related to bending, e.g. the cross sectional rotation and the resulting lateral contraction effects. Said contributions cancel out if a cross section is considered, where only shear effects are considered, which is the main idea of the given model.

The weak variational form of the finite element formulation is obtained by applying the principle of virtual displacements to the underlying displacement field and yields the following formulation:

$$\int_{\Omega} [\delta \mathbf{X}_0^T \mathbf{L}^T] [\bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{X}_0] d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{X}_0^T [\nabla \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}] d\Omega \quad (3)$$

\mathbf{X}_0 denotes the unknown displacement parameters, in the given case the warping deformation induced by shear. The resulting strains can be calculated using the linear operator \mathbf{L} which contains derivatives with respect to the planar coordinates (y and z) as entries. The matrix $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ corresponds to the material stiffness matrix used for calculating the stresses from the strains in the reference system. The stress residuum $\nabla \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ contains the loading information, hence also the parameter κ'_{xx} introduced in Eq. 1:

$$\nabla \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\bar{C}}_{11} \\ \bar{\bar{C}}_{61} \\ \bar{\bar{C}}_{51} \end{Bmatrix} (z \cdot \kappa'_{xx}) \quad (4)$$

For deriving the finite element stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} and load vector \mathbf{r} the discretization for the warping displacements \mathbf{X}_0 needs to be introduced:

$$\mathbf{X}_0 = \mathbf{\Phi}^T \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \leftrightarrow \delta \mathbf{X}_0 = \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^T \mathbf{\Phi} \quad (5)$$

Whereas $\mathbf{\Phi}$ denotes the matrix containing the element shape functions. In order to be able to reproduce the exact solution of laminated plates subjected to shear loading with only one element per layer in thickness direction, a Lagrange element with cubic shape functions was selected. Plugging in the expressions shown above into Eq. 3 yields the following system of equations:

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_1^{N_{el}} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{B} d\Omega; \quad \mathbf{r} = \sum_1^{N_{el}} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{\Phi} \nabla \hat{\sigma} d\Omega \quad (6)$$

The matrix \mathbf{B} appearing in the equation above is derived by applying the linear operator \mathbf{L} to the shape function matrix $\mathbf{\Phi}$.

The given planar model was derived for investigating corrugated laminates. However, due to its general theory, it may be used for calculating the response to transverse shear loading of any cross-section, including plates of any lay-up as well as beam-like structures. It has been verified using a commercial finite element routine and – in the case of plates – by comparison with the work of other authors. Thanks to the low computational cost, the model is well suited for performing parameter studies, as realized in [17]. In the scope of this paper, we will as well investigate and compare laminates with different lay-up and geometric parameters.

4 MATERIALS & PARAMETERS

For the following examples, the carbon composite material with the properties listed in Table 1 is used:

E_1 [MPa]	290000
E_2 [MPa]	5000
ν_{23} [-]	0.2
ν_{12} [-]	0.41
G_{23} [MPa]	2083
G_{12} [MPa]	5000

Table 1: Unidirectional GY-70 UHM CFK. Source: former Dornier System GmbH.

Figure 3 introduces the local st -coordinate system as well as all the relevant geometrical parameters:

Figure 3: Illustration of the local coordinates (blue) and the geometrical parameters (green).

5 FROM FLAT TO CORRUGATED LAMINATES

Figure 4 shows the intra- and interlaminar stress components in a composite plate subjected to shear loading:

Figure 4: Intra- and interlaminar stress in a composite plate subjected to transverse shear loading. The geometric parameters are $c/p = 0$ and $d/p = 0.04$, while $\kappa'_{xx} = 5E-07$ was used as load input parameter.

As expected, there are no intralaminar shear stresses in the laminate, besides some minor perturbations at the edges due to the periodicity boundary conditions. Thanks to the cubic finite element, shear stresses are exact for a flat laminate: the interlaminar shear stresses show a quadratic distribution and stress-free surfaces, which coincides with analytical results.

Figure 5: Intra- and interlaminar stress in a homogeneous corrugated laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. The geometric parameters are $c/p = 0.25$ and $d/p = 0.04$, while $\kappa'_{xx} = 5E-07$ was used as load input parameter.

In Figure 5 a homogeneous corrugated laminate subjected to the same loading situation is shown. The interlaminar stress peaks occurring at the midline $z = 0$ are a first peculiarity of corrugated structures

subjected to transverse shear loading. In case of circular corrugations, the interlaminar stress at the location of the peak corresponds to stress component τ_{xy} , which is depicted in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Shear stress component τ_{xy} in a homogeneous corrugated laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. The geometric parameters are $c/p = 0.25$ and $d/p = 0.04$, while $\kappa'_{xx} = 5E-07$ was used as load input parameter.

The necessity of the stress component τ_{xy} to be non-zero in general corrugated laminates can be shown using equilibrium considerations [16]:

$$\sigma_{x,x} + \tau_{xy,y} + \tau_{xz,z} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Formula (7) is generally valid at any point. We will evaluate it at $(y = \frac{3}{4}p, z = c)$ in Fig. 6:

- The gradient $\tau_{xz,z}$ vanishes due to an extremum which occurs since the respective stress component needs to vanish at the lateral surfaces of the laminate.
- The contribution $\sigma_{x,x}$ is linked to κ'_{xx} . It shows a linear dependency on z , hence it does not cancel out at the selected point since $z \neq 0$.
- The stress gradient $\tau_{xy,y}$ is therefore needed to equilibrate $\sigma_{x,x}$, causing the distribution of τ_{xy} shown in Fig. 6.

Note that the intensity of the intralaminar stress component in Fig. 5 is significantly higher than its interlaminar counterpart. Hence we can observe a “change of role” compared to the case of flat plates: τ_{xs} becomes the dominant stress component, whereas the significance of τ_{xt} remains limited [17].

6 INFLUENCE OF LAMINATE LAY-UP AND GEOMETRY

In the following short parameter study, we will investigate the response of several laminates with different geometrical properties to transverse shear loading. Complementary to the study presented in [17] the evaluation will focus on the evolution of intralaminar stress component τ_{xs} .

The following configurations were investigated:

- $d/p = 0.04$
- $c/p = 0$ and 0.25
- Laminates: $[0|90]_s$ and $[90|0]_s$

The results for the $[0|90]_s$ laminate are displayed in Figure 7. Subplot 7b.) shows the interlaminar shear stress in a flat plate subjected to transverse loading. It coincides well with analytical solutions for the given problem [18]. Comparison of Subplots 7c.) and 7d.), which illustrate the shear stresses in a circularly corrugated laminate, confirms the previously stated observation that the intralaminar shear stresses grow at a quick rate with increasing corrugation amplitude.

Figure 7: Intra- and interlaminar stress in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. The laminate thickness is $d/p = 0.04$, while $\kappa'_{xx} = 5E-07$ was used as load input parameter.

The equivalent results are displayed in Figure 8 for the case of the $[90/0]_s$ laminate. Again the through-thickness stress distribution in the plate (Figure 8b.) can be verified with solutions provided in literature [18].

Figure 8: Intra- and interlaminar stress in the $[90/0]_s$ laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. The laminate thickness is $d/p = 0.04$, while $\kappa'_{xx} = 5E-07$ was used as load input parameter.

7 DISCUSSION

Comparison of the stress distributions provided in Figures 4, 5, 7 and 8 enables to discuss the influence of the corrugation amplitude and the laminate design on the resulting shear stress distribution in corrugated laminates.

As a result of the different relevant shear moduli in thickness direction depending on the lay-up, the choice of laminate only has an influence on the interlaminar shear stress distribution in corrugated laminates. The distribution of intralaminar shear stresses is identical as the same value of shear modulus is relevant for all lay-ups (G_{12}).

The circular laminates with $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$ lay-up even have an almost identical maximum value of τ_{xs} , which is a result of the selected load input parameter: κ'_{xx} is linked to bending deformation. The relevant bending stiffness is similar in both cases as it is strongly influenced by the corrugation

amplitude, hence marginalizing the difference in stacking sequence of the two laminates. Normalizing the peak values of τ_{xs} with the shearing force transferred by the cross-section would result in identical extremum values for all three laminate lay-ups.

In view of the provided results, the question of the relevance of the interlaminar shear stresses for the load-carrying behavior of corrugated laminates may be raised. In the given cases, the magnitude of τ_{xs} is always one order of magnitude higher than of τ_{xt} . Keeping in mind that the intralaminar shear stresses are not present in plates, our future work will include detailed considerations on the transition from plates to corrugated structures and the resulting influence on shear stresses.

8 CONCLUSION

Transverse shear stiffness is expected to have a relevant influence on the deformation behavior of corrugated laminates. In order to investigate said effects, an efficient (planar) finite element formulation has been derived which can be used to calculate the response of a corrugated laminate subjected to transverse shear loading. It has been verified using a commercial finite element routine and – in the case of plates – by comparison with the work of other authors.

The investigated loading situation leads to the occurrence of both inter- and intralaminar shear stresses in the corrugated cross section. The former show a stress peak at the bending neutral axis which becomes more pronounced as the corrugation amplitude is increased. However, the relevance of those stress peaks has been shown to be limited.

On the other hand, the introduction of a corrugation leads to a significant increase in the intralaminar shear stress in the laminate, independently of the lay-up. For the given cases with circular corrugation the magnitude of the intralaminar shear stress has always been one order of magnitude above the interlaminar component, which agrees well with results provided in previous studies.

The presented model and the resulting findings help to extend the knowledge on the behaviour of corrugated laminates to an additional load case, thus complementing previous work of several authors on corrugated laminates subjected to different states of loading.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Swiss National Science Foundation (Project No. 169468 and Grant No. 200021_169468/1).

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Junkers, Flying-machine supporting surface, US Patent No. 14627, 1923.
- [2] H. Junkers, Flying-machine covering, US Patent No. 1553695, 1925.
- [3] T. Yokozeki, S. Takeda, T. Ogasawara and T. Ishikawa, Mechanical properties of corrugated composites for candidate materials of flexible wind structures, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **37**, 2006, pp. 1578-1586 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.10.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.10.015)).
- [4] I. Dayyani, A.D. Shaw, E.I. Saavedra Flores, M.I. Friswell, The mechanics of composite corrugated structures: A review with applications in morphing aircraft, *Composite Structures*, **133**, 2015, pp. 358-380 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.07.099](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.07.099)).
- [5] A. Airoidi, G. Sala, L.A. Di Landro, P. Bettini, A. Gilardelli, Composite corrugated laminates for morphing applications, in: A. Concilio, I. Dimino, L. Lecce, R. Pecora (Ed.), *Morphing wing technologies*, Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford, 2018.
- [6] C. Rees, Form and function in corrugated insect wings, *Nature*, **256**, 1975, pp. 200-203 (doi: [10.1038/256200a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/256200a0)).
- [7] D.-E. Levy and A. Seifert, Simplified dragonfly airfoil aerodynamics at Reynolds numbers below 8000, *Physics of Fluids*, **21**, 2009, pp. 071901 (doi: [10.1063/1.3166867](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3166867)).
- [8] C. Thill, J.D. Downsborough, S.J. Lai, I.P. Bond and D.P. Jones, Aerodynamic study of corrugated skins for morphing wing applications, *The Aeronautic Journal*, **114**, 2010, pp. 237-244 (doi: [10.1017/S0001924000003687](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0001924000003687)).

- [9] Y. Xia, O. Bilgen and M.I. Friswell, The effect of corrugated skins on aerodynamic performance, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, **25**, 2014, pp. 786-794 (doi: [10.1177/1045389X14521874](https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X14521874)).
- [10] D. Briassoulis, Equivalent orthotropic properties of corrugated sheets, *Computers & Structures*, **23**, 1986, pp. 129-138 (doi: [10.1016/0045-7949\(86\)90207-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949(86)90207-5)).
- [11] Y. Xia, M.I. Friswell and E.I. Saavedra Flores, Equivalent models of corrugated panels, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **49**, 2012, pp. 1453-1462 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2012.02.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2012.02.023)).
- [12] C. Wang, H.H. Khodaparast, M.I. Friswell and A.D. Shaw, An equivalent model of corrugated panels with axial and bending coupling, *Computers and Structures*, **183**, 2017, pp. 61-72 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruc.2017.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruc.2017.01.008)).
- [13] G. Kress and M. Winkler, Corrugated laminate homogenization model, *Composite Structures*, **92**, 2010, pp. 795-810 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.08.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.08.027)).
- [14] D. Filipovic, G. Kress, Manufacturing method for high-amplitude corrugated thin-walled laminates, *Composite Structures*, **222**, 2019, pp. 110925 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.110925](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.110925)).
- [15] G. Kress and M. Winkler, Corrugated laminate analysis: A generalized plane-strain problem, *Composite Structures*, **93**, 2011, pp. 1493-1504 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2010.12.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2010.12.004)).
- [16] D.T. Filipovic and G.R. Kress, A planar finite element formulation for corrugated laminates under transverse shear loading, *Composite Structures*, **201**, 2018, pp. 958-967 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.06.048](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.06.048)).
- [17] D.T. Filipovic and G.R. Kress, Stress analysis of corrugated orthotropic laminates under transverse shear loading, *Composite Structures*, **223**, 2019, pp. 110983 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.110983](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.110983)).
- [18] R. Rolfes and K. Rohwer, Improved transverse shear stresses in composite finite elements based on first order shear deformation theory, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **40**, 1997, pp. 51-60 (doi: [10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0207\(19970115\)40:1<51::AID-NME49>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0207(19970115)40:1<51::AID-NME49>3.0.CO;2-3)).
- [19] C. Thurnherr, Y. Mirabito, G. Kress and P. Ermanni, Highly anisotropic corrugated laminates deflection under uniform pressure, *Composite Structures*, **154**, 2016, pp. 31-38 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.07.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.07.017)).